

Future evolution of glaciers

Print to PDF

On this page

- Globally or regionally:
- European Alps:
- Authors
- Data sources
- Source code

Globally or regionally:

Find out about the global future evolution of glaciers! This interactive graphic displays the volume change of all glaciers worldwide under four different global warming scenarios between $+1.5^\circ\text{C}$ and $+4^\circ\text{C}$ until 2100. You can also compare the global evolution to single glacier regions.

[Skip to main content](#)

European Alps:

You can also only look at the evolution of glaciers in the European Alps and compare the different alpine countries

To start the app, click on this link: [launch](#) [bokeh app](#)

Authors

[Fabien Maussion](#), [Zora Schirmeister](#) and [Lilian Schuster](#)

Data sources

Data: [Rounce et al. \(2022\)](#)

Source code

Code and data are on GitHub for the [Global App](#), and the [European Alps App](#), BSD3 licensed.

We welcome any app improvements. Just write us a mail with the jupyter-notebook or send

[Skip to main content](#)

< Previous
[Mass-Balance Simulator](#)

Next >
[Introduction to glaciers](#)